

1 **Thymine DNA glycosylase TDG functions between UNG and an Xist RNP-based transcriptional**
2 **activation or repair machine containing ILF2 and SLBP in transformation.**

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7 We recently identified *UNG*, a uracil DNA glycosylase, as an intermediate actor functioning between a
8 transcriptional machine with likely functions in a specific transcriptional activity associated with
9 transformation, supported by interactions with the Xist non-coding RNA as part of a recently identified
10 ribonucleoprotein complex (Xist RNP) containing the interleukin enhancer factor *ILF2*.

11 Here we describe requirement of the thymine DNA glycosylase, *TDG*, for sustained function of a
12 transcriptional apparatus that maintains the transformed state. *TDG* functioned proximal to *UNG* and was
13 necessary for *UNG* activation.
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